

PENETRATION DEPTH LIMITS OF ACTIVE THERMOGRAPHY FOR DETECTION OF IMPACT DAMAGE IN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper outlines an investigation of the penetration depth limits of two active thermographic inspection techniques, flash thermography and sonic thermography, for quantitative sizing of barely visible impact damage in 4 mm thick carbon fibre composite plate. The impact damage size and depth was first determined using phased array ultrasonic testing. Thermographic inspections were then carried out and the damage size measured from processed thermal signatures compared to the C-scan results. Size estimates obtained from sonic thermography are shown to compare favourably with the C-scan results, indicating full through-thickness penetration for this method. The size estimates obtained from flash thermography indicated only partial thickness penetration.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Australian Defence Force is modernising its fleet of aircraft, with many of its newer aircraft containing significant amounts of composite material, e.g. JSF, MRH90 and Tiger. Composite materials have many practical advantages for aircraft construction, such as high stiffness and strength-to-weight ratio as well as corrosion resistance; however they are generally inferior to metals in impact resistance. Barely visible impact damage (BVID) is of particular concern. This form of damage can occur during normal operations via hail impact, bird strike, foreign object debris on take-off or landing, and through maintenance via accidental tool drop. It can lead to a significant reduction in static and fatigue strength yet can be difficult to detect.

It is thus important to have appropriate non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods that can be carried out quickly and effectively to detect and quantify BVID, so that aircraft availability is not unduly affected. Active infrared thermography has many advantages in this respect. It is a broad-area visual technique which can be used to rapidly identify areas of suspected damage. It should be viewed as complementary to established NDE techniques, such as ultrasonic testing, which can provide a more detailed quantitative assessment of damage than is possible with thermography, but is much slower to implement for wide-area inspection.

To use active thermography effectively, it is important to understand its limitations. In relying on heat diffusion for energy transport through an object, one of the key limitations of thermography is penetration depth, which is the subject of investigation in this paper. In this study, the penetration depth limit of thermography for BVID inspection is inferred by comparing the lateral dimensions of thermal indications produced by thermography to the actual dimensions of the defect as determined by a C-scan obtained from phased array ultrasonic testing (PAUT), which for the samples under investigation can achieve full through-thickness penetration.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Specimens

A series of quasi isotropic IM7/977-3 [45,0,0,-45,90]_{3S} laminate plate coupons measuring 300 mm x 100 mm x 4 mm were impacted in an instrumented drop-weight test rig, at three energy levels in the BVID regime (Table 1). The damage was confirmed to extend through the full thickness of each

specimen using PAUT. The size of the damage was also determined using PAUT. The PAUT system used was an Olympus OmniScan MX2 with a 5 MHz linear probe which was coupled to the test subjects using water. Figure 1 shows C-scan results for the specimens at the different impact energy levels, with the colour map indicating the depth of the damage. The red arrows drawn on Specimen 1 indicate the vertical and horizontal dimensions of the damage. Damage size estimates for all of the specimens are summarised in Table 1.

Sample Number	Impact Energy (J)	Defect size (mm) (horizontal axis)			Defect Size (mm) (vertical axis)		
		C-Scan	ST	FT	C-scan	ST	FT
1	21.44	39.0	42.7	22.1	48.7	53.1	33.0
2	21.44	40.1	46.2	22.6	48.4	54.5	32.6
3	21.44	39.4	38.7	23.7	46.5	46.1	34.7
4	21.44	46.9	46.8	31.7	56.3	52.0	39.5
5	10.72	31.1	39.2	17.5	34.7	43.4	23.2
6	10.72	32.1	38.7	19.3	35.5	44.1	24.2
7	5.36	24.0	23.6	14.8	23.8	26.7	16.9

Table 1: Defect size comparison between C-scan, sonic (ST) and flash thermography (FT). The values are the average dimensions measured from processed thermographic data.

Figure 1. C-scan results for the three energy levels; 21.44 J (top), 10.72 J (middle), 5.36 J (bottom). The red arrows on specimen 1 indicate the measured vertical and horizontal dimensions. The colour map indicates depth of damage.

2.2 Thermographic Techniques

The coupons were analysed using two active thermographic techniques; sonic [1] and flash [2]. Sonic thermography (ST) uses high-frequency acoustic standing waves that are introduced into a specimen using an acoustic horn driven at frequencies typically in the range of 20-40 kHz. In the present study the drive frequency was 20 kHz, the input power was 555 W and all subjects were excited for 1 s. The acoustic standing waves induce lateral motion at the contacting surfaces of a defect, resulting in frictional heating which produces a thermal signature recorded by an infrared

imaging system, as depicted in Figure 2. This inspection modality is well suited to BVID because of the large number of faying surfaces created by fracturing of the matrix during impact.

Figure 2. Schematic of ST system.

Flash Thermography (FT) uses high energy flash lamps to induce a rapid temperature change at the surface of the structure. Internal flaws disrupt the flow of heat into the structure, leading to differential rates of cooling on the surface which are recorded as thermal contrasts by an infrared camera, as depicted in Fig. 3. An FT inspection system developed by DST was used in the present study. The inspection head contains 4 linear xenon flash tubes internally mounted and powered by a 6 kJ capacitor unit. The lamps are triggered remotely using a custom software application, which also synchronises data capture from the infrared camera. For both thermographic techniques a FLIR SC6000 infrared camera was used. This camera has a cooled 640 x 480 InSb focal plane array with a noise equivalent temperature difference (NETD) of ~20 mK. Its frame rate is variable but was fixed to 25 Hz over 12 s for this study. The specimens were coated with a thin layer of high emissivity paint to maximise thermal emission from the specimen and to minimise the influence of thermal reflections.

Figure 3. Schematic of FT system

In FT the time required for a signature to emerge from a depth L can be determined approximately from the relation [3],

$$t = \frac{L^2}{\alpha \pi} \tag{1}$$

where α is the through-thickness thermal diffusivity, which for the laminate coupons considered in this study has a value of $4.7e-07 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, as determined experimentally using Parker's method [4]. Using this value and substituting the laminate thickness for L , equation 1 yields $t=10.84 \text{ s}$. This represents a minimum observation time. The actual observation time was set to $1.7t$ or 18 s , to allow for some margin of error in the diffusivity estimate and specimen to specimen variation. It should be noted that a shorter observation time was used for the ST, due to the heat originating from the defect in ST, rather than being applied to the surface as an impulse excitation, as in the case for FT.

2.3 Thermographic Post Processing

Infrared imaging has a relatively low signal-to-noise ratio compared to visual imaging and therefore can benefit from the application of signal enhancement techniques. Two post-processing techniques were applied in this study: (i) pulsed phase thermography (PPT) [5] and (ii) principal component thermography (PCT) [6].

PPT applies a Fourier transform to the time signal acquired at each pixel to generate a spatial map of signal phase for a set of discrete frequencies. Differential rates of cooling caused by sub-surface structural flaws produce phase anomalies in these maps. The penetration depth achieved by PPT is frequency dependent, which is evident in the FT results shown in Figure 4. For example the signatures in the higher frequency phase maps correlate well with near-surface structural features, e.g. PPT_{10} , while those in the lower frequency maps correlate well with deeper features, e.g. PPT_1 . A similarly strong relationship between depth and frequency was not observed in the ST results. This is due to the thermal signature being produced by a different mechanism. Figure 5 shows ST PPT data for one of the impacted specimens. The highly detailed signature in the scan is typical, and is surmised to result from the presence of many faying surfaces in the damaged structure.

Figure 4. Flash thermography pulsed phase results for specimen 1, showing frequencies 1-10 (identified as PPT_1 to PPT_{10}).

PCT, like PPT, maps a thermographic time-sequence to a set of basis functions. However, instead of using a set of orthogonal harmonic functions, as in PPT, PCT uses an empirically determined set of orthogonal functions or modes. By doing this it avoids an arbitrary assignment of a specific functional form to the basis, and has been found to deliver a better signal to noise ratio than PPT in many situations. Figure 6 shows the first 10 modes obtained from a PCT analysis of ST data acquired from Specimen 1. In the present work, defects were sized using signatures from the second and third PCT modes. In practice, the first three modes typically describe over 90% of the variance in the raw data set.

Throughout this paper the subscripts assigned to both PPT and PCT results denote the order of the frequency and mode, respectively.

Figure 5. Sonic thermography pulsed phase results for Specimen 1, showing frequencies 1-10 (identified as PPT₁ to PPT₁₀).

Figure 6. Sonic thermography principal component results for Specimen 1, showing modes 1-10 (identified as PCT₁ to PCT₁₀).

2.4 Determination of Impact Damage Size

A qualitative analysis was undertaken to determine the lateral size of the impact damage. The raw thermographs were processed using PPT and PCT to obtain thermal signatures of the damage. The signatures giving the largest impact damage size were chosen for detailed analysis. In the first step of the analysis the edge of the defect was identified by applying a simple thresholding technique which involved adjusting the colour map of the thermograph to delineate the perimeter of the damage and then tracing a contour around that perimeter. The maximum vertical and horizontal dimensions were then measured. A schematic outline of the process is shown in Figure 7. As it is the outer dimension of the defect which is of interest, the thermographs with the largest external dimensions were used for the size determination; in this case PPT₂ and PCT₃. The average between these two chosen PPT and PCT results was calculated for all of the specimens. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 7. Schematic outline of the process for determining impact damage size.

Figure 8 shows a representative comparison between the ST (top row) and FT (bottom row) results for Specimen 1. The raw thermographs shown in the first row indicate that in the absence of post-processing, ST produces a comparatively larger thermal signature. The processed data in Figure 8(b) and (g) are adjusted via colour map manipulation to permit a damage perimeter to be drawn, as shown in Figure 8(c) and (h) respectively. A similar process is applied to the PCT results in Figure 8(d) and (i), to produce the perimeter estimates in Figure 8(e) and (f) respectively. A box was drawn around each of the defect areas and the vertical and horizontal dimensions were then measured.

Figure 8. Specimen 1: sonic thermography (top) and flash thermography (bottom).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

BVID usually results in “pine tree” shaped damage vertically through the specimen, with a small damage area at the surface and increasingly larger damage area through the depth of the specimen. The damage caused by an impact typically contains crushed regions, delaminations, fibre breakage and matrix cracking [7, 8].

The sizing from the ST results was comparable to that obtained from the corresponding C-scans, whereas sizes determined from the FT results were generally underestimated. The better performance of ST may relate to its detection modality. Near the outer edges of a BVID zone the frictional forces acting across faying surface are likely to be relatively high due to higher closure stresses, which is a favourable condition for frictional heating. By contrast, closure stresses generally facilitate heat flow across a faying surface leading to a reduced signature in FT. Another possible factor is the shorter heat transfer path in ST compared to FT. Because the heat source is generated at the defect in ST, the transfer length is equivalent to the defect depth. In FT, this effective path length is twice the defect depth, which has an adverse impact on signal strength.

Figure 9 shows the C-scan of specimen 1 overlaid with the PPT and PCT results for both ST and FT. This is indicative of the variance observed between ST and FT, among all of the specimens. The C-scans indicate a smaller damage area near the surface, increasing in area with depth into the specimen. The ST results correlate well with the damage extent at the back of the specimen (Figure 9 (a) and (b)), with PPT₆, PCT₁ and PCT₃ producing size estimates that are close to the C-scan result. PPT₈ for ST corresponds well to the damage indicated in the C-scan at between 1.2 mm and 1.4 mm below the surface. The size estimates from FT are consistently smaller. The higher frequency PPT results for FT show a smaller damage size near the surface (PPT₁₀), which is to be expected with BVID. Deeper into the specimen (corresponding to low frequency, PPT₁ and PCT₁) the damage size increases. The C-scan results indicate that the damage detected using FT is between 1.2 mm and 2.0 mm below the surface.

Figure 9. Specimen 1 overlay of C-Scan. ST: (a) PPT and (b) PCT and FT: (c) PPT and (d) PCT.

The defect sizes determined by ST are very close to, and sometimes larger than those determined from C-scan, suggesting that ST can detect damage through to the back face of these particular specimens. This is a cautious finding however, as lateral heat flow from the damage area is likely to contribute to an overestimate of the heat-producing area based on the qualitative sizing approach used in this study. The results are more conclusive with respect to the relative performance of FT and ST

with the latter producing consistently smaller size estimates. Table 2 lists penetration depths inferred from the lateral size estimates obtained for each specimen and each thermographic inspection technique.

Specimen Number	Maximum Estimated Penetration Depth (mm)	
	ST	FT
1	4.0	2.0
2	4.0	2.2
3	4.0	2.1
4	4.0	1.9
5	4.0	2.0
6	4.0	2.1
7	4.0	2.5

Table 2: Maximum estimated penetration depth obtained using ST and FT.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study has shown that ST outperforms FT for sizing of BVID in carbon fibre laminates of 4 mm thickness. The size estimates obtained from ST were comparable to those obtained from ultrasonic C-scan, though in some cases overestimates were produced due to the effects of heat diffusion.

Further research is currently underway to develop an automated method of assessing the external outline of the damage from ST, thereby removing a subjective element of the sizing procedure.

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